

DESCRIBING, ANALYZING, AND SYNTHESIZING HEALTH COMMUNICATION
THEORIES

by

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Abstract

This paper discusses and examines three communication theories. It explains the Diffusion of Innovation Theory, which involves behavioral and social sciences; the Stages of Behavioral Change Model, which heavily involves psychology; and the Knowledge Gap Theory, which involves mass media and new media and touches on sociology and philosophy.

Diffusion of Innovation Theory is a theory that explains how the communication and adoption of new ideas, products, practices, and behaviors spread through a population. Stages of Behavioral Change Model is a theory that explains how people change their behavior and the steps they take in the change process. Knowledge Gap Theory is a theory that suggests that there is a gap between the knowledge of the informed and the uninformed, and it explains the reasons for this continued gap of knowledge. The paper then synthesizes the three theories by explaining the strengths and weaknesses of similarities and differences. The paper suggests that the three theories can be used to develop effective communication strategies that can help promote adopting new ideas, products, practices, and behaviors.

Thesis Statement

The diffusion of Innovation Theory depends on specific decision-making stages that correlate with the five stages of change in the Stages of Behavioral Change Model. This implies that innovation adoption is influenced by similar factors that influence behavioral change. The Knowledge Gap Theory explains that some people gain information faster and adopt innovations more quickly because of their socioeconomic status and their ability to comprehend information more easily. However, the diffusion of Innovation Theory and the Stages of Behavioral Change Model do not factor in the gaps in knowledge that lead to disparities in information dissemination.

Description and Analyses of Theories

Diffusion of Innovation Theory

Everett Rogers's 1962 Diffusion of Innovation Theory explains how an innovation spreads through a community (Valente, 2006). This theory uses the words "community" and "social system" interchangeably. Communication is essential for effectively diffusing a new idea or product through a population. For the diffusion of innovation to occur, the social system must perceive an idea or concept as new (Rogers, 2008).

An *innovation* can be defined as an idea, practice, or object that is perceived as new by an individual (Rogers, 2008). It can also be described as new ideas, opinions, attitudes, and behaviors (Valente, 2006). From a health communication perspective, an innovation could mean a new daily behavior that could help benefit longevity or quality of life. Innovativeness can be described as the degree to which an individual is relatively earlier in adopting new ideas than other members of a social system (Rogers, 2003).

Rogers (2003) explains that *diffusion* is the process by which innovations are communicated through specific channels over time among members of a social system (as cited in Valente, 2006). The primary function of mass media communication in the diffusion process is to create awareness and knowledge about an innovation (Rogers, 2008). The diffusion process also influences attitude change, decision-making, and implementation of the innovation (Rogers, 2008). Examples of channels for diffusion include social media platforms, opinion leaders communicating with their followers, interpersonal communication via word of mouth, print media, and televised media, including news media. Time is also associated with the diffusion process.

Adoption Categories in Diffusion of Innovation Theory

The diffusion of Innovation Theory adoption categories includes *innovators*, *early adopters*, *early majority*, *late majority*, and *laggards* (Rogers, 2003). These groups form a bell curve on a graph, with the innovators and laggards making up the smallest percentage of innovation adopters and the early and late majority making up the largest percentage of the population to adopt an innovation.

The *innovators* create or are the first ones to adopt a new idea, concept, or practice. They are risk-takers willing to try new things and decide much faster than other groups whether they will adopt them (Schaivo, 2014). This high rate of adoption is why innovators can act as role models and persuade other groups to adopt the innovation (Schaivo, 2014).

The *early adopters*, who watch the innovators closely, are the next group to adopt an innovation. They pick up the innovation relatively faster than the following groups. They hold leadership roles in the social system and are responsible for bringing the innovation to the mass market's attention (Mehmood, 2016). This group can be otherwise known as the opinion leaders who communicate the innovations to the early and late majority.

The next group, the *early majority*, accounts for the largest percentage of people and is the first part of the large section in the bell curve. The early majority pick up innovations because they are watching the early adopters. They are typically cautious and wait to see how others react to an innovation before adopting it. This group comprises individuals who wait until most of their peers adopt the innovation (Mehmood, 2016).

The *late majority* is the second largest part of the bell curve, representing a large population. They usually see the early majority using the innovation, who communicated it to them, and they follow behind. This group tends to adopt an innovation after the

average member of society does (Mehmood, 2016). Lastly, the *laggards* are the last ones to adopt the innovation, or they never adopt it. The communication reaches them, but they refuse to adopt or only adopt the innovation when necessary.

Stages of Change in Diffusion of Innovation Theory

Adoption of an innovation is a type of change. Change occurs over time and depends on stages (Schaivo, 2014). Diffusion of Innovation Theory identifies five stages of change: *awareness, knowledge and interest, decision, trial and implementation, and confirmation* (Schaivo, 2014).

Awareness is the stage where people learn about an innovation's existence and how it could fit into their lives. This is where individuals gain knowledge of the idea, concept, or practice. Xiong (2016) defines awareness-knowledge as the message about the innovation's existence. After becoming aware of an innovation, an individual goes through a *knowledge and interest stage*. This is where a process of persuasion happens. This stage depends on not only being aware of the product, like in the awareness stage, but also being interested in it. The individual will decide whether or not they find the innovation interesting enough to try it based on the information they have gathered.

The *decision stage* is when an individual decides whether or not to try an innovation. This decision is based on social learning, which is the process of learning from others' experiences (Xiong, 2016). Individuals also defer communication during this stage, meaning they wait to hear about the outcomes of others' experiences before making a decision (Xiong, 2016) The basic idea of modeling the social learning process is that individuals use the information about the outcomes of others' experiences to update their own adoption decisions (Xiong, 2016). The innovation-decision process is the mental process through which an

individual passes from knowledge of a new idea to the adoption and confirmation of the innovation (Rogers, 2003, as cited in Rogers, 2008).

The *trial or implementation stage* is when the individual starts using the newly adopted idea or concept. This is where the individual starts to put what they have learned into practice and see how it works for them. They may make adjustments and changes as needed and receive feedback from others. This is a critical stage in the adoption process, where the individual will either decide to continue using the new idea or concept or abandon it.

The *confirmation stage* is when individuals decide whether to adopt or reject an innovation. Only a few people adopt an innovation during the early stages of the diffusion process based on their awareness of it (Xiong, 2016). If an innovation is widely accepted, the process will continue to the next stage, and if it is rejected, it will terminate (Xiong, 2016). The last stage of the diffusion process is *adoption*, when many people accept and use an innovation.

Stages of Behavior Change Model

The Stages of Behavior Change Model, also known as the Transtheoretical Model (TTM), was developed in the late 1970s by James Prochaska and Carlo DiClemente. Stages of Behavior Change Model describes five stages of change that people go through when changing a behavior. These stages include *pre-contemplation, contemplation, preparation, action, and maintenance* (Lippke, 2006). The Stages of Behavior Change Model is used in psychology, behavioral and social sciences, and marketing. It can help indicate at which stage a person or group of people is in the change process. This can be

helpful in segmenting groups to understand better how to target health communication to those groups or individuals.

Behavior is a primary component in the Stages of Behavior Change Model. All behavior can be described as an attempt by an individual to bring about a particular state of affairs, either to change an existing state or to maintain a current one (Ossorio, 2006, p. 49). In other words, behavior is any observable overt movement of the organism generally taken to include verbal behavior and physical movements (Bergner, 2011). The Stages of Behavior Change Model explains the stages in which these states of affairs happen.

Lippke (2006) defines stages as discrete steps in the process of intentional behavioral change. These stages are characterized by different motivation levels or readiness to change (Weinreich, 1999). Lippke also notes that stage models show that behavior change is best conceptualized as transitioning through a time-ordered sequence of different stages. However, not everyone goes through each stage, and some people are at different stages at different times. It is essential to know which stage an individual is at so that they can be targeted effectively during health communication campaigns.

Change is another component in the Stages of Behavior Change Model. It views behavior change as an active process in which individuals set goals, develop and enact strategies to achieve those goals, appraise progress, and revise goals and strategies as needed (Baumeister, 2005). The stages of the Stages of Behavior Change Model can be broken down by intention: the *non-intenders* are in the pre-contemplation stage, the *intenders* are in the contemplation and preparation stages, and the *actors* are in the action and maintenance stages (Velicer, 2008). Intention requires autonomy and self-efficacy, which will be explained further down in this paper.

Five Stages of Change in Stages of Behavior Change Model

Stages of Behavior Change Model outlines five stages of behavior change: *pre-contemplation, contemplation, preparation, action, and maintenance*. Behavior change theories focus on dynamic variables, which can be changed, while behavior theories focus on static variables (Velicer, 2008). In Stages of Behavior Change Model, the variables are open to change because they are dynamic. After studies were conducted on change, intention was found to be a powerful predictor of behavior change (Velicer, 2008). However, after more rigorous studies with controlled variables, the intentions showed to drop in correlation (Velicer, 2008). Each stage indicates perceived pros and cons of changing the behavior (Velicer, 2008). These will be discussed in each stage section below.

Pre-contemplation is when individuals are not considering changing their behavior but are open to learning more about it (Schiavo, 2014), and the information is still being communicated to them. This stage can be further divided into two sub-stages: those who intend to adopt the behavior in the future and those who do not intend to adopt the behavior at all (Velicer, 2008). Not everyone is willing to contemplate a behavior change, which can create gaps in traditional behavior change theories (Velicer, 2008). In the pre-contemplation stage, the cons of changing are perceived to outweigh the pros (Velicer, 2008).

The *contemplation stage* is when individuals consider adopting a recommended behavior (Schaivo, 2014). This is when the necessary information has been communicated to the individual, and they have enough information to think about the options. This contemplation of behavior change is brought on by a developed awareness that a change may be necessary (Bamberg, 2013). Within this stage, the person can go either way, either change their behavior or

not change their behavior. In the contemplation stage, the pros and cons are about equal, reflecting the ambivalence of this stage (Velicer, 2008).

In the *decision stage*, also called the *preparation stage*, the individual decides whether to adopt the behavior or not. This is the stage in which the person intends to take specific actions in the immediate future (Bamberg, 2013). In this stage, the pros of changing the intended behavior outweigh the cons (Velicer, 2008).

The *action stage* is when people try to adopt a new behavior for a short period of time (Schaivo, 2014) and actually change their behavior (Bamberg, 2013). Prochaska's (2006) analysis found that between the pre-contemplation and action stages, positive expectancies increased by about one standard deviation in both his 1996 and 2006 studies. In both studies, negative expectancies decreased by about one-half of a standard deviation (Velicer, 2008). This means that the pros of changing behavior in the action stage outweigh the cons (Velicer, 2008).

The *maintenance stage* is when people continue to practice a healthy behavior for a long period of time, ideally incorporating it into their routine and lifestyle (Schaivo, 2014). This is also the stage when people work to prevent relapse (Bamberg, 2013). In the maintenance stage, the benefits of the healthy behavior outweigh the costs even more than in the previous stages (Velicer, 2008).

Knowledge Gap Theory

Knowledge Gap Theory was developed in 1970 by Tichenor, Donohue, and Olien, also known as the “Minnesota Team.” It states that the more knowledge people have about a particular topic, the more likely they are to accept and adopt new information about that topic. This increased likelihood of information adoption is because people with more knowledge can better understand and interpret new information. The Minnesota Team published a study of the

social structure of public affairs and science knowledge entitled “Mass Media Flow and Differential Growth in Knowledge in 1970 (Gaziano, 2008). These studies set out to understand why some populations of people received information that others did not and how communication of information and people’s knowledge differed between social strata (Gaziano, 2008). They formulated a hypothesis, a set of assumptions, explanatory factors, and a pair of testable statements that could explain and even help alleviate this relative deprivation of knowledge between social strata (Gaziano, 2008).

The Knowledge Gap Theory states that an increase in knowledge leads to an increased rate of acceptance of a pattern of behavior, a belief, a value, or an element of technology in a social system (Gaziano, 2008). In other words, when a population communicates, hears, and understands an intended behavior change, they are more likely to accept and adopt that change. Knowledge Gap Theory has applications in a number of areas, including education, public health, and marketing. In health communication, for example, public health officials can use the Knowledge Gap Theory to develop campaigns to help people understand and adopt new health behaviors by targeting the key groups properly, understanding the gaps where some populations do not receive adequate information, and tailoring their efforts to help reach all people.

Information and knowledge are two huge components of the Knowledge Gap Theory. When thinking about this theory, knowing that knowledge and information are two different concepts is important. Knowledge denotes certain socially structured collective representations, including beliefs, values, prospects for the future, and the well-being of the community, that constitute the worldviews of different social strata (Tichenor, Rodenkirchen, Olien, & Donohue, 1973). Information, on the other hand, is qualitatively undifferentiated data of the information delivery system (Tichenor, Donohue, & Olien, 1980), the product of its “feedback” and

“distribution control” (Olien et al., 1983). This means that knowledge is the product of information being communicated and processed between senders and receivers.

Knowledge gaps, another vital component of Knowledge Gap Theory, are discrepancies between the level of knowledge of specific pieces of information in a population. These gaps are particularly poignant when certain types of knowledge are supposed to have universal value but are not universally held (Gaziano, 2008). In health communication, for example, most people know that medical mask-wearing is effective in preventing viruses from transmitting to mass populations during pandemics, but there are still some people who believe that mask-wearing makes people more ill or that it is completely useless. This knowledge gap can be attributed to the way information is diffused to a population. Some people are more likely to be exposed to information than others, and some people are more likely to believe information than others.

Societal Naturalism Perspective on Knowledge Gap Theory

The Knowledge Gap Theory touches on philosophical aspects of its phenomena. It is based on the societal naturalist perspective, which views society as a naturally occurring superindividual collective entity whose organizational qualities cannot be reduced to individual parts (Levine, 1995). This perspective suggests relative differences in knowledge acquisition among social strata and linkages among the source, channel, and audience components of the communication subsystem (Olien, Donohue, & Tichenor, 1983).

Using this societal naturalist perspective, the Knowledge Gap Theory suggests that there are a number of issues within society, including gaps in knowledge that lead to inequality. If people with higher socioeconomic status are more knowledgeable about important issues, they may be better able to make decisions that affect their lives and the lives of others. This can lead to situations where people with lower socioeconomic status are at a disadvantage. The societal

naturalist perspective is expressed in the original Knowledge Gap Hypothesis: “As the infusion of mass media information into a social system increases, segments of the population with higher socioeconomic status tend to acquire this information at a faster rate than the lower status segments, so that the gap in knowledge between these segments tends to increase rather than decrease” (Tichenor et al., 1970, pp. 159–160 as cited in Gaziano, 2008). This means that some elite groups have access to more information and, thus, more knowledge than more underserved and disparate populations (Tichenor et al., 1970, as cited in Gaziano, 2008).

Structural Functionalist Perspective on Knowledge Gap Theory

The Minnesota Team noted that knowledge gaps may be considered structurally functional from two points of view. The first is that more highly educated people are at the front of progressive social change, and second, knowledge gaps serve to maintain power differentials of super and subordination through information control (Tichenor et al., 1973). Knowledge gaps can increase tension within the social system by maintaining existing elites, which can lead to further social problems (Tichenor et al., 1970). The Minnesota Team maintains throughout their work that social power is the basic issue in the knowledge gap phenomenon (Olien et al., 1983).

Reasons for Reinforcement of Knowledge Inequalities

There are five reasons why knowledge gap inequalities continue to exist. These reasons are *communication skills*, the *amount of stored prior knowledge of pertinent topics*, *relevant social contact*, *information retention*, and *the nature of the mass media information delivery subsystems* (Tichenor et al., 1970). Below, each one is explained further.

Communication skills affect knowledge inequalities in determining how well an individual can understand concepts and gather information. If a person has trouble understanding and remembering information, it will be more difficult for them to retain knowledge. This is

partly due to an individual's education, as this correlates to their level of communication skills. An individual's structural location in the social strata can also affect whether they receive information or whether it makes sense to them (Tichenor et al., 1980). This is an example of how a gap in knowledge could form and be reinforced.

The amount of *stored prior knowledge of topics* an individual has is another reason knowledge gap inequities continue to exist. This is related to whether individuals or groups have access to books, classrooms, and other resources that provide a reservoir of knowledge (Tichenor et al., 1970). Again, education comes into play. Individuals and groups with more education have a larger store of prior knowledge to help them understand new concepts being communicated to them. *Relevant social contact*, which can include different activities, reference groups, and interpersonal discussion, also reinforces knowledge inequalities (Tichenor et al., 1970).

Selective exposure, acceptance, and retention of information are all influenced by arousal and salience (Gaziano, 2008). This means acceptance and retention of information correlate with perceived information as important. In a homogenous community, where people tend to have similar interests and values, interpersonal communication is more likely to occur than mass communication (Gaziano, 2008). This can lead to knowledge gaps narrowing as people are exposed to a broader range of information from their peers and are more likely to understand it at an interpersonal level. However, mass communication is more likely to occur in a more complex and pluralistic community, where people have a wider range of interests and values (Gaziano, 2008). This can lead to knowledge gaps widening as people are exposed to a narrower range of information from the media. (Gaziano, 2008).

The *Nature of Mass Media Information Delivery Systems* plays a role in why knowledge gaps continue to exist. The Minnesota Team found that knowledge gaps decrease for local issues

when the issue is highly significant, there is high community conflict, and the population is homogeneous (Gaziano, 2008). This means that locally diffused information is more likely to reach and be understood by the intended population (Donohue, Tichenor, & Olien, 1975). The Minnesota Team's research suggests that local media can be crucial in informing the public about local issues. When local media cover an issue in depth, it can help reduce knowledge gaps and ensure everyone can access the information they need to make informed decisions (Gaziano, 2008). This means that locally diffused information has a greater chance of reaching an intended population and the information being understood by the population.

Synthesis of Diffusion of Innovation Theory, Stages of Behavior Change Model, and Knowledge Gap Theory

Synthesis

The Diffusion of Innovation Theory, Stages of Behavior Change Model, and Knowledge Gap theory all have similar components, which are explained below. Each theory has strengths and weaknesses in explaining its components. In addition to their similarities, they also have differences and unique perspectives.

Communicated Information

Diffusion of Innovation Theory, Stages of Behavior Change Model, and Knowledge Gap Theory all deal with newly communicated information to a population and how the population receives the communicated information. Diffusion of Innovation Theory and Stages of Behavior Change Model both have an intended action, behavior change, or adoption as the end stage of the theory, meaning they deal with active publics at some point within their stages. Knowledge Gap Theory does not focus on active publics, or people who intend to gather information. Behavior Change Model and Diffusion of Innovation Theory, on the other hand, show certain stages of

how a population thinks about and eventually adopts an intended idea, behavior, or product. Knowledge Gap Theory, on the other hand, explains the broader phenomenon of populations either having access to communicated information or not having access to communicated information.

Access to Information

Diffusion of Innovation Theory states that innovators have more access to economic resources, allowing them to try or to create new ideas, products, practices, or behaviors more quickly than other groups of people. In other words, being of a higher socioeconomic class means this population has more monetary resources to acquire knowledge about innovations or, in health communication, health information. This gives them an advantage over other groups regarding access to information. Knowledge Gap Theory also explains that there are groups of people from higher socioeconomic status that receive information more quickly or receive information that lower socioeconomic classes have no access to. This more readily available information, or more accessible access to information, is a component that both the Diffusion of Innovation Theory and Knowledge Gap Theory cover in their explanations. The Knowledge Gap Theory better explains this specific component because they factor in disparities in the communication flow.

Another component that the Knowledge Gap Theory explains is that the Diffusion of Innovation Theory and the Stages of Behavior Change Model do not have gaps in knowledge due to understanding and educational differences. Knowledge Gap Theory is most effective in explaining phenomena based on the amount of access to information. It goes in-depth to explain that not everyone has the same access to information, whether that be because of educational factors, self-efficacy factors, socioeconomic factors, and so forth. This is a strength of the

explanation that the Knowledge Gap Theory provides. This is a weakness in the Diffusion of Innovation Theory because it does not really take into account gaps in knowledge. For example, those who have the most access to intended behavior change messages or are able to buy and adopt expensive innovations more quickly receive the communication. The Diffusion of Innovation Theory does not consider that not everyone has access to the same messages.

Communication of information leads to awareness. One of the stages in the Stages of Behavior Change Model is awareness. If a person is not aware of an intended behavior change, they do not have the option of changing that behavior. Awareness means that the message is being communicated properly to an individual so that they can access the information and understand it. When people do not have access to or cannot understand information, it creates gaps in knowledge. Again, this is a weakness for the Stages of Behavior Change Model.

The Knowledge Gap Theory could be placed at the very beginning of the Stages of Behavior Change Model and Diffusion of Innovation Theory and could be used in conjunction with these two theories. This is because the Knowledge Gap Theory shows that not everyone will have access to the same communicated information about the intended behavior change.

Large Populations

The Diffusion of Innovation Theory, the Stages of Behavior Change, and the Knowledge Gap Theory are all theories that explain the phenomenon of how information is disseminated to large populations. Although both the Diffusion of Innovation Theory and the Stages of Behavior Change Model explain the phenomenon of how information is

disseminated across large populations, they both do not take into account the issues that arise when information is sent out. The Knowledge Gap Theory takes these issues into account; therefore, the Knowledge Gap Theory is more potent in this aspect and is particularly useful for understanding how information can be accessible or inaccessible to specific groups of people.

The Knowledge Gap Theory examines the differences in knowledge across various groups of people. These knowledge disparities may arise from multiple factors, including educational disparities, socioeconomic status, and access to information. The Knowledge Gap Theory can also aid in understanding how to enhance the dissemination of information to large populations. For instance, in health communication, if there exists a knowledge gap regarding pandemic protocols among different groups, targeted information can be directed to those specific groups to help bridge the gap. This theory provides a deeper insight into how certain information may not be accessible to all groups. In contrast, the Diffusion of Innovations and the Stages of Behavior Change Model do not offer this comprehensive understanding of the inequalities in communication within large populations

Group Separation

All three theories illustrate phenomena in groups distinguished by specific factors. The Diffusion of Innovation Theory categorizes populations into groups based on the speed with which they adopt information or communication regarding new ideas, products, practices, or behaviors. The Stages of Behavior Change Model further separates groups by their intentions for behavior change and how individuals perceive the advantages and disadvantages associated with each stage of behavior change. The groups defined in the Diffusion of Innovation Theory encompass innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority, and laggards (Rogers, 2003). In the Stages of Behavior Change Model, there are Intenders, Non-Intenders, and Actors (Velicer

2008). The Knowledge Gap Theory does not categorize or label groups based on who receives more information or has greater access to it than others. However, one way to analyze populations is by socioeconomic status. Grouping by socioeconomic status is not a specific categorization tied to this theory. The failure to acknowledge distinct groups is a limitation of the Knowledge Gap Theory, as it could provide further insights into the amount of information different groups receive. For instance, it could explore groups of individuals who receive and comprehend all information, as well as those who receive and understand some information, and groups who receive and understand almost no information.

Self-Efficacy

The Diffusion of Innovation Theory and the Stages of Behavior Change Model both explain self-efficacy phenomena, while the Knowledge Gap Theory provides minimal insight into self-efficacy. Self-efficacy refers to the confidence one has in their ability to accomplish a task and the willingness and capability to consider behavior change. As Velicer (2008) noted, not everyone is open to contemplating behavior change, which creates gaps in traditional behavior change theories. This reluctance to consider behavior change is evident in the laggard group within the Diffusion of Innovation Theory. Although knowledge reaches them, they refuse to consider the behavior change. This understanding of self-efficacy-related decision-making processes gives the Diffusion of Innovations Theory and the Stages of Behavior Change Model advantages over the Knowledge Gap Theory. Although there aren't many reasons for self-efficacy-related continued knowledge gaps in Knowledge Gap Theory, one reason for persistent knowledge gaps is selective exposure and stored prior knowledge. Both reasons can be tied back to self-efficacy because if an individual does not believe in their ability to adopt a communicated

intended health behavior change, their search for information will show systematic preference towards that non-belief. This is where Knowledge Gap Theory shows strength and Diffusion of Innovation Theory and the Stages of Behavior Change Model reveal weakness. Knowledge Gap Theory goes the extra step by explaining the reasons people are unaware of an intended behavior change and how the reluctance to change is not always of their own accord. Believing the information relates to self-efficacy. Some individuals in the Knowledge Gap Theory are more inclined to believe the information they receive than others. This can be attributed to self-efficacy as well as other factors, including education.

Stages

In the Diffusion of Innovation Theory, diffusion researchers identify five stages in the adoption process: knowledge, persuasion, decision, trial, and adoption (Valente, 2006). The Stages of Behavior Change model also comprises five stages in the behavior change process: pre-contemplation, contemplation, decision, action, and maintenance (Schiavo, 2014). Both theories illustrate that change phenomena occur in time-based sequences or stages. These sequences indicate that innovations and behaviors share similarities in their adoption or change processes. Both involve either new ideas or practices or, in the context of products, a behavior change related to the use of that new product. The staging process is an aspect that Knowledge Gap Theory does not address. Knowledge Gap Theory lacks depth in examining time-based phenomena like the other two theories do, which presents a limitation for it.

The Diffusion of Innovation Theory and the Stages of Behavior Change Model both show that “decision” is in the middle of the stages of the adoption of change or innovation. This means that these theories are useless without a decision or self-efficacy. The population has to decide whether to adopt a behavior or innovation or not adopt it. Self-efficacy is also part of

many other communication theories, including Social Cognitive Theory and Health Belief Model. This means that each theory has a decision-making process embedded within the main components, whereas Knowledge Gap Theory does not.

The Diffusion of Innovation Theory's stages of adoption appear similar to Stages of Change Model, but the adoption stages usually indicate a person's progress toward adopting a healthy behavior, whereas the stages of change indicate a person's progress toward quitting a deleterious one (Valente, 2006). This means that although both theories show decision-making processes, they deal with opposite spectrums of decision-making: deciding whether to quit a behavior or begin a behavior. This doesn't mean there is a weakness or a strength in either over one another, it just means they are different in that way.

The Stages of Behavior Change Model points out that there are pros and cons to deciding to adopt a behavior. In contrast, the Diffusion of Innovation Theory does not describe the pros or cons of the decision-making process but merely a "are you going to try it or not" explanation. This extra explanation given by the Stages of Behavior Change Model shows that it is stronger in the area of decision. For example, the Stages of Behavior Change Model better explains how there are sub-steps within the decision stage. This is where Knowledge Gap Theory can be used to show that neither the Diffusion of Innovation Theory nor the Behavior Change Model takes into account there should be an explanation of whether information is even reaching a population properly for them to make an informed decision. If a group of people are unaware of a communicated intended behavior change to help their health and quality of life, they could never even reach the "decision stage."

Another similarity between the Diffusion of Innovation Theory and the Stages of Behavior Change Model is that not all innovations go through all five stages of decision-making,

and not all individuals go through all five stages of behavior change. Thus, the decision-making process for both theories can start at any stage.

Communication Campaigns

These three theories and most other communication theories can be used to develop strategies for communicating new information to a population. For example, to communicate new health information to a population, the Diffusion of Innovation Theory could identify the innovators and early adopters in the population and target the communication efforts toward them. The stages of the Behavior Change Model could also be used to develop a communication strategy that considers the different stages people go through when changing their behavior. If the proper stage is identified, then communication can be tailored to them. Finally, the Knowledge Gap Theory could be used to develop a communication strategy that considers the different levels of knowledge that people have about health information so communication campaigns can be structured to suit all levels.

Conclusion

Diffusion of Innovations Theory, Behavior Change Model, and Knowledge Gap Theory suggest that communication is the primary source of new health ideas, products, practices, and behaviors spreading through populations. Communication is the main source of awareness. The theories explain why and how communication reaches specific parts of populations at different times, or if it reaches populations at all. All three theories can be used to learn where people are at, at different stages of the adoption or change process. The theories can also be used to motivate people to change their behavior and provide a diverse range of people, both socioeconomically and sociologically, with the skills and resources necessary to change.

The Knowledge Gap Theory does an excellent job of explaining the “that” and “why” of the phenomena of information not reaching entire populations and why this phenomenon happens. Still, it falls behind on the “how” explanation of the phenomena. For example, it shows *that* there is a discrepancy in the amount and quality of health information that reaches populations. It explains *that* there are knowledge gaps in health information and *that* specialized knowledge is held by certain classes and not by others (Schudson, 1983), but not how. The Knowledge Gap Theory also explains *why* knowledge gap inequalities continue to exist but not precisely how they happen, in stages or divisions.

The Diffusion of Innovations Theory and the Stages of Behavior Change Model both explain how information spreads through populations and why it reaches some individuals but not others. These theories illustrate how behaviors change in stages and why some people adopt these changes faster than others. I believe that detailing the “how” is a strength of both the Diffusion of Innovations Theory and the Stages of Behavior Change Model, as they provide a deeper understanding through groupings and a more analytical approach to the discussion phenomena.

The scholars who have evaluated all three of these theories are knowledgeable and have devoted considerable thought to the information. It is easy to get lost in translation when discussing these theories, as they may seem to be common sense or straightforward at first glance, until one analyzes them. All three of these communication theories contain multiple parts and layers. I believe that the arguments of all three theories are solid and supported by studies, although I find it challenging to obtain mathematical data to substantiate the ideas of all communication theories.

The Diffusion of Innovation Theory and the Stages of the Behavior Change Model could be enhanced by incorporating an idea into the awareness and decision-making stages that explains that not everyone has equal access to the information necessary to become aware of an intended health behavior change. To make a decision, an individual must be well-informed. Overall, all three theories give a complex understanding of how information is disseminated to populations and how they could be used in health communication campaigns to help diverse audiences better understand health information.

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